

Challenges in Implementing E-Learning in Institutes of Sciences and Technologies of Physical and Sports Activities: The Views of Professors

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Abstract:

This study explores the main obstacles to implementing e-learning in institutes of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities from the perspective of professors in eastern Algeria. By adopting the descriptive approach. A sample of 43 professors was randomly selected from various institutes - Souk Ahras, Oum El Bouaghi, Batna, Setif, Tebessa - for the 2024-2025 academic year. A 28-item questionnaire was developed, covering three main axes: infrastructure availability (technological tools and media), students' ability to use e-learning technologies, and professors' proficiency in utilizing these technical means. After ensuring the reliability and stability of the tool within the survey study procedures, the questionnaire was distributed electronically. The data were statistically processed using SPSS and we reached the following results:

-Challenges stemming from insufficient infrastructure.

-Difficulties related to students' ability to effectively use e-learning technologies.

-Limitations concerning professors' proficiency in utilizing e-learning tools hinder its implementation.

Keywords: hindrances; E-learning; Sciences and Technologies of Physical and Sports Activities Institutes

المخلص:

هدفت دراستنا إلى الكشف عن معوقات تطبيق التعليم الإلكتروني بمعاهد علوم وتقنيات النشاطات البدنية والرياضية من وجهة نظر أساتذة المعاهد في جامعات الشرق الجزائري. اعتمدنا على المنهج الوصفي، وقد تكونت عينة الدراسة من 43 أستاذ من مختلف المعاهد - في كل من جامعة سوق هراس، تبسة، أم البواقي، سطيف وباتنة -، في الموسم الجامعي 2024-2025، قمنا بتصميم استمارة استبيان مكونة من 28 عبارة موزعة على 3 محاور المحور الأول حول المعوقات المتعلقة بالبنية التحتية (أدوات ووسائط تكنولوجية)، المحور

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الثاني حول المعوقات المتعلقة بقدرة الطلبة على استخدام تقنيات التعليم الإلكتروني، المحور الثالث حول المعوقات المتعلقة بقدرة الأساتذة على استخدام تقنيات التعليم الإلكتروني. وبعد التأكد من صدق وثبات الأداة ضمن إجراءات الدراسة الاستطلاعية وزعنا الاستبانة إلكترونياً. وبعد المعالجة الإحصائية باستخدام برنامج SPSS توصلنا للنتائج التالية:

- وجود صعوبات ناجمة عن عدم كفاية البنية التحتية.
 - هناك صعوبات متعلقة بقدرة الطلاب على استخدام تقنيات التعلم الإلكتروني بفعالية.
 - القيود المتعلقة بكفاءة الأساتذة في استخدام أدوات التعلم الإلكتروني تعيق تطبيقه.
- الكلمات المفتاحية:** المعوقات، التعليم الإلكتروني، معاهد علوم وتقنيات النشاطات البدنية والرياضية

1-Introduction:

The current era is dominated by information and technology. Information and communication technology (ICT) is deeply rooted in various aspects of life and has become indispensable. With rapid development, the world is just a click away, and communication between different societies has become easier than ever before, transcending traditional geographical boundaries. ICT has also adopted new methods that have given various sciences a quantum leap in the exchange of knowledge and information. It has opened a new door for communication characterized by its electronic nature, as this characteristic has facilitated many processes in education in particular. Nabar (2022) pointed out that new technologies have transformed teaching methods, making personal attendance no longer a necessity for exchanging educational and research-related information between senders and receivers. Additionally, they have reshaped how educational materials are received, processed, stored, and distributed in a positive direction. The added value that these technological developments provide to education can't be denied.

E-learning is one of the most important technological updates. It has created a quantum leap in the learning and teaching process, due to the tools and techniques it has made available, which in turn have proven their effectiveness in education. Moreover, it has provided educational opportunities for different segments of society in proportion to their abilities and capabilities. It also opens up the possibility of accessing knowledge at any time and in any place, according to what suits the learner's situation. As Dr. Redif Taysir Fawzi (2023) has mentioned, E-learning is a modern and contemporary system that meets the new

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realities and facilitates education through technological developments and supports social values in the right to education for all.

Due to the continuous development of tools and means of exchanging knowledge and experiences in different fields, Highlights the science and technology of physical activities and sports as a field that deal directly with the human psyche. As is well known, physical activity is a medium that has a direct impact on the individual in its various components. The researcher Jabouri bin Omar and others (2019, p. 41) stated that physical sports activity plays an important and pivotal role in building an individual's personality in all aspects - physical, moral, psychological and social - and is considered one of the practices that work to guide physical development through the use of motor exercises, health measures and some psychological and moral methods...

The field of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities, as other fields, has sought to incorporate these technological advances into the education and training of its professionals. "There is a growing interest in educational technology in the educational community that seeks to develop educational practice by continuously researching the most effective strategies and methods to engage students by providing an interactive learning environment." (Al-Shammari et al., 2021, p. 82).

It is natural for new phenomena to face a set of obstacles, and this is also the case with e-learning of the sciences and technologies of physical activities and sports. Researcher Fatima Rabhi (2022) stated that according to the latest statistics on distance education in the world for the year 2020, the percentage of this type of education has increased compared to learning through paper publications, especially in Europe and Asia, but as for Africa, this education has not received sufficient attention due to the living conditions of the population in these countries, which are witnessing a deterioration in many areas, including the field of technology.

Given the importance of e-learning in the educational process because it is considered a supportive means that transforms it from indoctrination to creativity, due to the different forms it provides for the student so that he becomes the core of the educational process, in addition to his freedom to access knowledge and information at the appropriate place and time, which allows him to make optimal use of it. As for the teacher, it is considered an aid in providing an attractive

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learning environment that enables him to present information in a more effective way, in addition to the effort and time it saves.

Despite the additions that made by e-learning in education, it faces many obstacles stand in the way of achieving its goal in some disciplines, including the field of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities, which is considered a vital field with a different nature from other disciplines because it contains skills that require field work. Hence, the issue of the study emerged, which aims to investigate the most important obstacles that obstructs the application of e-learning in sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities institutes, and the phenomenon of the study was identified in the following questions:

General question:

- Are there any obstacles that limit the application of e-learning in institutes of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities from the view of institute professors?

There are many studies with varied results. Here are some of the papers that have focused on this topic:

* Study of Najwa Madi Sadawi Alagoury, Khaled Khalifa Al-Saber Borwis (2024):

This study aimed to identify the most important obstacles that stand behind the uses of technical and vocational e-learning in Libyan society. The research workers used the descriptive analytical approach. The study sample comprised 42 faculty members at higher institutes in the city of Ajdabiya. They were chosen randomly. The research tool was a questionnaire consisting of 42 statements. As for statistical processing, they used the SPSS program. The study attained the following results:

- Most of the obstacles are mainly administrative and financial obstacles that would provide infrastructure for the application of e-learning.

- Human obstacles occupy the second place.

- The third place was represented by obstacles related to the curricula.

* Study by Akram Yassin Mohammed Al-Alusi (2022):

This study aimed to discover the barriers to the use of e-learning from the viewpoint of faculty members at the Faculty of Basic Education at Anbar University. The researcher relied on the descriptive approach. The study sample involved all staff at the College of Basic Education - Haditha at Anbar University for the academic year 2020-2021. The research tool was a questionnaire consisting of 20 paragraphs. For

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statistical processing, the researcher relied on the Chi-square, Pearson's correlation coefficient, the weighted mean, and the percentage weight. The following results were reached:

- There are obstacles that hinder the use of e-learning among faculty members in the college.
- The lack of modernized computers in the college, also the lack of preparation faculty members on using computers in education.

*Study by Batoul Ghaleb Al-Nahi (2022):

The study aimed to determine the obstacles to e-learning in colleges of education. The research worker depended on the descriptive approach. The study sample included 200 professors from the University of Basra / College of Education for the academic year 2020- 2021, selected utilizing a stratified random method. The researcher developed a questionnaire for e-learning obstacles with 54 paragraphs distributed over 5 areas (obstacles related to university administration, difficulties specific to the university teacher, barriers to infrastructure and technical support, obstacles related to scholars, obstacles related to the educational program). the researcher used the SPSS program. Among the results attained by the study are the following:

- The field of obstacles related to students ranked first, then the field of obstacles to infrastructure and technical support ranked second, then in third place the field of obstacles specific to the university professor, followed by the field of obstacles related to university administration in fourth place, and finally the field of obstacles related to the curriculum in fifth place.

* Study of Qasim Muhammad Nida, Shalal Ali Khalaf (2022):

The study aimed to identify the obstacles to e-learning from the point of view of instructors. The researchers used the descriptive approach. The study sample included 100 teachers from the College of Education for Human Sciences at Tikrit University for the academic year (2020-2021). The study tool consisted of 3 fields with 28 paragraphs. After statistical processing of the data, the following results were reached:

- The obstacles that instructors faced in the first place were represented by the field of administrative and financial aspects.
- The obstacles that instructors faced in the second place were represented by the field of academic curricula.
- The obstacles that instructors faced in the third place were represented by experience in the field of e-learning.

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*Study of Fathi Abu Al-Qasim Salem Mansour, Mustafa Al-Sadiq Al-Ghadban Abdul-Sadiq, Al-Hadi Rahuma Khalifa Khalaf Allah (2021): this study aimed to identify the obstacles to e-learning faced by faculty members at the Faculty of Economics and Political Science at Sabratha University. Relied on the descriptive analytical approach. Randomly selected sample estimated at 57 individuals represented by faculty members at the Faculty of Economics and Political Science at Sabratha University. And a questionnaire included four axes prepared by the researchers, in the statistical processing they used SPSS program. V23. The results that were reached are:

- The presence of administrative and technical obstacles.
- The presence of obstacles related to faculty members.
- The presence of obstacles related to e-learning

General hypothesis:

- There are obstacles that hinder the application of e-learning in institutes of science and technology of physical and sports activities from the view of institute professors.

Hypotheses:

- Infrastructure-related challenges (technological tools and media) hinder the implementation of e-learning in institutes of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities, according to institute teachers.
- Students' ability to use e-learning technologies present an obstacle to its implementation in these institutes, from the teachers' perspective
- Teachers' proficiency in using e-learning technologies limit the effective application of e-learning in these institutes.

2- General objective of the study:

The study aims to determine the key obstacles that may obstruct the implementation of e-learning in the considered institutes from the perspective of professors. The significance of this study lies in the crucial role of e-learning as a modern advancement in educational technology. By examining the challenges faced in applying this form of education, as perceived by teachers, the study provides a realistic and comprehensive insight. These findings offer valuable data and information to decision-makers, enabling them to develop solutions, overcome obstacles, and ultimately enhance the effectiveness of e-learning in our specialty.

3- Procedural definition of the concepts mentioned in the research:

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- Obstacles:

“These are the obstacles and difficulties that stand in the way of teachers and students, preventing them from interacting and participating with each other, which hinders the achievement of the desired goals of the educational institution.” (Rasoul and Awizar, 2021, p. 203)

Procedural definition: in this study, it refers to the difficulties that hinder the use of e-learning in the transfer of knowledge in the field of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities and the education of students in specialized institutes.

- E-learning:

“E-learning can be considered a manner of education that relies on information and communication technologies and their various media to provide educational content and convey skills and concepts to the learner in a way that allows the student to interact actively with the content, teacher and colleagues synchronously or asynchronously at the time, place and speed that suits the learner’s circumstances and ability, and to manage all activities of the educational process and its requirements electronically through the electronic systems designated for that” (Al-Atrabi, 2019, p. 26)

Procedural definition:

E-learning is one of the new methods in the field of education and relies on technological techniques and modern communication mechanisms such as computers, networks and multimedia. It allows the learner to interact with the various components of the educational process (educational material, professors and even colleagues) simultaneously or asynchronously.

- Institutes of Science and Technologies of Physical and Sports Activities:

“It is an educational institution affiliated with the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, which supervises the formation in the field of physical and sports activities for students who have obtained the baccalaureate. In the graduating stage. By offering programs and courses related to the objectives of the training”. (Alali et al., 2023, p. 130)

Procedural definition It can be defined as educational institutions that offer academic programs based on scientific educational curricula with the aim of preparing specialized cadres in various fields of physical education, in addition to providing studies, research, and scientific field experiments that aim to advance physical and sports

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activities and achieve the desired benefit from them. In our study, it is represented by the institutes of sciences and technologies of physical and sports activities located in the universities of eastern Algeria, which are represented by the University of Souk Ahras, Oum El Bouaghi, Batna, Tebessa and Setif.

4- The methodological procedures used in the study:

4-1 Method and tools:

We adopted the descriptive approach as it is the most appropriate approach for this type of research that aims to describe the phenomenon as it is in reality.

The research sample was selected randomly, and it consisted of teachers from the Institutes, as follows:

Table N° 1 Study sample specifications

Institute	At Souk Ahras University	At Setif University	At Batna University	At Tebessa University	At Oum El Bouaghi University	total
Number of teachers	13	7	11	3	9	43
%	30.2	16.3	25.6	7	20.9	100 %
Academic Rank	Professor of Higher Education	Senior Lecturer	lecturer	Assistant Professor - A	Assistant Lecturer	43
N	16	17	6	2	2	
%	37.2	39.5	14	4.7	4.7	100 %

Source: faiza hachelaf, (2025)

- Study tool: We developed a questionnaire consisting of 28 statements divided into three main axes. The first axis includes 9 statements addressing the key obstacles to implementing e-learning in the institutes, as perceived by teachers, related to the availability of infrastructure (technological tools and media). The second axis

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comprises 12 statements focusing on the challenges associated with students' ability to use e-learning technologies. The third axis consists of 7 statements highlighting the difficulties faced by professors in utilizing e-learning technologies effectively.

-Correction method:

A five-point Likert scale was adopted, with each answer evaluated as follows:

strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), Strongly agree (5).

-Psychometric properties of the search tool:

To verify the validity and reliability of the tool, we conducted a survey study that extended from 08/15/2024 to 01/25/2025, during which we designed a questionnaire that consisted in its initial form of 39 statements, depending on many scientific references and previous studies in the same context. The procedures were as follows:

-Tool reliability:

We used the apparent validity by presenting the tool in its initial form to a group of professors - 7 teachers - in the discipline. According to specialists the questionnaire was modified to consist of 28 phrases distributed over 3 axes (as mentioned in the appendices).

-Tool stability:

We calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the first and the second application on the same sample, which was estimated at 17 teachers from different institutes (Characteristics of the exploratory sample is listed in the appendices), as well as the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The results were as follows:

Table N° 2 Search tool stability coefficient

The axis	Number of phrases	Sample size	Pearson correlation coefficient	Significance level	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
The first axis	9	17	0.86	0.01	0.74
The second axis	12		0.87		0.8
The third axis	7		0.65		0.76

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The questionnaire as a whole	28		0.88		0.89
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Source: faiza hachlaf, (2025)

**4-2 Presentation and Analysis of Results:
- the First Hypothesis Results:**

Table N° 3 analysis of the first axis results

Phrase number	N / %	answer					mean	Std deviation	T value	df	sig	decision
		I strongly agree	I agree	neutral	Disagree	I strongly disagree						
01	N	15	15	2	11	0	3.79	1.18	4.37	42	0.00	significant
	%	34.9	34.9	4.7	25.6	0						
02	N	9	15	8	10	1	3.49	1.14	2.80	42	0.00	significant
	%	20.9	34.9	18.6	23.3	2.3						
03	N	13	19	4	4	3	3.81	1.18	4.52	42	0.00	significant
	%	30.2	44.2	9.3	9.3	7						
04	N	12	20	4	7	0	3.86	1.01	5.55	42	0.00	significant
	%	27.9	46.5	9.3	16.3	0						
05	N	6	23	9	5	0	3.7	0.86	5.31	42	0.00	significant
	%	14	53.5	20.9	11.6	0						
06	N	20	15	4	4	0	4.19	0.95	8.12	42	0.00	significant
	%	46.5	34.9	9.3	9.3	0						
07	N	8	16	6	11	2	3.40	1.19	2.16	42	0.03	significant
	%	18.6	37.2	14	25.6	4.7						
08	N	8	16	7	11	1	3.44	1.14	2.54	4	0.01	significant

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	%	18.6	37.2	16.3	25.6	2.3				2	5	t
09	N	10	14	11	7	1	3.58	1.09	3.47	4	0.00	significant
	%	23.3	32.6	25.6	16.3	2.3						
Answers to the first axis							3.69	0.7	6.47	4	0.00	significant

Source: faiza hachelaf, (2025)

Considering what is stated in Table N°3, we note that all the statements are statistically significant, as the sig value was less than the significance level of 0.05. It also appears that the first axis is statistically significant.

The results indicated that professors of institutes in eastern Algeria perceive several obstacles to e-learning implementation, particularly regarding infrastructure. Key challenges include a weak internet network, limited availability of applications, outdated software, insufficient equipment, and the lack of technical support for content adaptation.

The findings confirm that infrastructure-related challenges (technological tools and media) hinder the implementation of e-learning in the institutes, validating the first hypothesis.

- the second Hypothesis Results:

Table N° 4 analysis of the second axis results

Phra se number	N / %	answer					me an	Std deviat ion	T val ue	sig	decisio n
		I stro ngly agree	I agree	neut ral	Disag ree	I stro ngly disag ree					
10	N	9	19	8	6	1	3.67	1.04	4.25	0.00	Signifi cant
	%	20.9	44.2	18.6	14	2.3					
11	N	3	11	12	14	3	2.93	1.07	-0.42	0.67	Not signifi cant
	%	7	25.6	27.9	32.6	7					
12	N	7	26	2	8	0	3.74	0.95	5.11	0.00	signifi cant
	%	16.3	60.5	4.7	18.6	0					

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13	N	5	10	15	13	0	3.16	0.99	1.06	0.29	Not significant
	%	11.6	23.3	34.9	30.2	0					
14	N	11	20	6	6	0	3.84	0.97	5.63	0.00	Significant
	%	25.6	46.6	14	14	0					
15	N	17	21	4	1	0	4.26	0.72	11.33	0.00	Significant
	%	39.5	48.8	9.3	2.3	0					
16	N	21	18	2	2	0	4.35	0.78	11.29	0.00	Significant
	%	48.8	41.9	4.7	4.7	0					
17	N	3	16	14	10	0	3.28	0.9	2.01	0.05	Significant
	%	7	37.2	32.6	23.3	0					
18	N	13	25	3	2	0	4.14	0.74	10.06	0.00	Significant
	%	30.2	58.1	7	4.7	0					
19	N	24	14	5	0	0	4.44	0.7	13.49	0.00	Significant
	%	55.8	32.6	11.6	0	0					
20	N	6	17	12	6	2	3.44	1.05	2.75	0.09	Significant
	%	14	39.5	27.9	14	4.7					
21	N	15	24	2	2	0	4.21	0.74	10.68	0.00	Significant
	%	34.9	55.8	4.7	4.7	0					
Answers to the second axis							3.78	0.46	11.06	0.00	significant

Source: faiza hachelaf, (2025)

Considering what is stated in Table N°4, we note that all the statements are statistically significant, as the sig value was less than the significance level of 0.05, except for statement N. 11 and N. 13. It also appears that the second axis is statistically significant.

The results indicated that professors perceive several obstacles related to students' ability to use e-learning technologies in the institutes. These challenges include students' lack of experience in using computers and accessing virtual lectures, difficulties in downloading files, and limited interest in the information provided through e-

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learning platforms. Additionally, students show low awareness of the importance of e-learning, are often distracted by other websites, and exhibit weak engagement with online content.

The findings confirm that students' limited ability to use e-learning technologies hinders its application in the institutes under consideration, validating the second hypothesis.

-the third Hypothesis Results:

Table N° 5 analysis of the third axis results

Phr ase num ber	N / %	answer					me an	Std devia tion	T val ue	sig	decisi on
		I stro ngly agre e	I agre e	neut ral	Disa gree	I stro ngly disa gree					
22	N	12	23	4	3	1	3.9 8	0.93	6.8 2	0.0 00	signifi cant
	%	27.9	53. 5	9.3	7	2.3					
23	N	12	21	4	5	1	3.8 8	1.02	5.6 3	0.0 00	signifi cant
	%	27.9	48. 8	9.3	11.6	2.3					
24	N	12	17	5	8	1	3.7 2	1.14	4.1 4	0.0 00	signifi cant
	%	27.9	39. 5	11.6	18.6	2.3					
25	N	4	20	12	7	0	3.4 9	0.88	3.6 2	0.0 01	signifi cant
	%	9.3	46. 5	27.9	16.3	0					
26	N	5	12	5	19	2	2.9 8	1.18	- 0.1 2	0.8 98	Not signifi cant
	%	11.6	27. 9	11.6	44.2	4.7					
27	N	4	22	7	10	0	3.4	0.96	3.1	0.0	signifi

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	%	9.3	51.2	16.3	23.3	0	7		7	03	cant
28	N	12	14	9	8	0	3.7	1.08	4.23	0.000	signifi cant
	%	27.9	32.6	20.9	18.6	0					
Answers to the third axis							3.60	0.58	6.71	0.000	signifi cant

Source: faiza hachelaf, (2025)

Considering what is stated in Table N° 5, we note that all the statements are statistically significant, as the sig value was less than the significance level, except for statement N 26. It also appears that the third axis is statistically significant.

The results revealed that professors face challenges in using e-learning technologies, which hinder its implementation in research institutes. Key obstacles include a lack of experience in using computers and the internet, affecting lesson delivery, as well as the electronic format of lessons, which may not effectively convey content. Additionally, professors struggle with designing online assessments and lack continuous training on technological tools, highlighting the need for specialized support and professional development programs. The findings confirm that professors' limited ability to use e-learning technologies hinders its implementation in our institutes, validating the third hypothesis.

4-3 Discussion and interpretation of the results:

After analyzing the results of the first hypothesis, its validity was confirmed, demonstrating the existence of obstacles that hinder the implementation of e-learning in targeted institutes. From the perspective of professors in our institutes, these obstacles are primarily related to the availability of infrastructure, including technological tools and media. Key challenges include a weak internet network, a lack of applications, updates, and software that facilitate e-learning, as well as insufficient equipment and the absence of technical support for content adaptation, among other issues. This aligns with the studies of Najwa Madi Saadawi Al-Aqouri and Khaled Khalifa Al-Saber Bourouis (2024), as well as Akram Yassin Muhammad Al-Alusi (2022), which highlight that most obstacles are administrative and financial in nature. These challenges primarily

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affect the provision of essential infrastructure, such as well-equipped halls, a high-speed internet network, and other necessary resources for effective e-learning.

The validity of the second hypothesis was also confirmed, as it was proven that there are obstacles that limit the application of e-learning in the respective institutes from the point of view of professors, related to the students' ability to use e-learning technologies, such as the students' lack of experience in using computers and in how to join virtual lectures, as well as their facing difficulties when downloading files, in addition to their lack of interest in the information and knowledge provided through e-learning platforms, their weak awareness of the importance of this type of education, their preoccupation with other sites, and also their weak interaction with the content provided through e-learning platforms...etc. This aligns with the study of Batoul Ghaleb Al-Nahi (2022), which found that a lack of support from professors, weak computer skills, low awareness of e-learning's importance, and distractions from unrelated websites are significant barriers. These results highlight the need to educate and motivate students to engage in e-learning, given its numerous benefits and conveniences.

The third hypothesis was also proven to be true, which states that there are obstacles that hinder the application of e-learning in studied institutes from the point of view of professors, related to the ability of professors to use e-learning techniques such as lack of experience in using computers and the Internet, which in turn affects the presentation of the lesson, as well as the electronic nature of the lesson, which is not considered helpful in delivering the content as it should be, and also the difficulty of formulating tests that are completed remotely, in addition to the absence of continuous training for professors at the university on ways to use technological means by specialists. This aligns with the studies of Qasim Muhammad Nida and Shalal Ali Khalaf (2022), as well as Fathi Abu Al-Qasim Salem Mansour, Mustafa Al-Sadiq Al-Ghadban Abdul-Sadiq, and Al-Hadi Rahuma Khalifa Khalaf Allah (2021). These studies highlight the need for teacher training on various aspects of e-learning, including the prevention of cheating in online exams and strategies to enhance engagement. The findings emphasize the importance of specialized training programs and technical support to assist professors in adapting content, ultimately easing their workload and improving e-learning effectiveness.

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Conclusion:

The study confirmed the presence of several obstacles limiting the implementation of e-learning in institutes of physical and sports activities sciences and technologies, as perceived by professors:

- Challenges related to infrastructure availability, including technological tools and media.
- Difficulties stemming from students' ability to effectively use e-learning technologies.
- Limitations associated with professors' proficiency in utilizing e-learning technologies.

Based on these results and in accordance with the results of the current study, we propose the following:

- Working on infrastructure development that supports e-learning and provide various resources related to it, especially at the level of institutes.
- Spreading the culture of e-learning and awareness students about the importance of this type of education.
- Providing training courses for students and professors on the uses of technological means and applications as well as educational platforms (Moodle platform).
- Providing technical support to professors and making specialists available to adapt the contents.
- Encouraging students and professors to use e-learning to benefit from its various advantages.

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